

coordinate bond from nitrogen to aluminium. Coordination of oxygen of pyridine-*N*-oxide to aluminium as observed by a shift of 1240 (ν_{N-O})²⁵ and 840 cm^{-1} (δ_{N-O})²⁶ to lower wave number region. Probably due to the stability of the six-membered ring structure of $\text{Al}(\text{ONp})_3$, it did not give addition compounds with these ligands.

Thus the parent naphthoxides except $\text{Al}(\text{ONp})_3$, on adduct formation with bases, suffer a breakdown of polymeric structure and readily form monomeric addition compounds suggesting the stability of aluminium-nitrogen bond in preference to aluminium-oxygen bond and also relaxation of strain is experienced in polymeric structures (I) and (II).

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium with Glycine and Malonic Acid.

A Polarographic Study

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A few binary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and malonic acid have been reported in the literature¹⁻³. Some mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and other complexing agents have also been studied⁴. The survey of literature reveals no report on the study of mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and malonic acid and hence thought worthwhile to undertake the present investigation.

Experimental

AnalR grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions. Double-distilled water was used to prepare the solutions of cadmium chloride, glycine and malonic acid. The overall concentrations of Cd^{II} , KCl and gelatin in the test solutions were 1.0 mM, 1.00 M and 0.01%, respectively.

Current-voltage curves were obtained by means of a Toshniwal PL-50 manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer. The capillary characteristics ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$) in KCl ($\mu = 1.00 \text{ M}$) at $E_{d.e.} = -0.61 \text{ V}$ vs S.C.E. and $h = 60 \text{ cm}$ at $42 \pm 0.1^\circ$ were $2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for deoxygenation. A Elico LI-10 needle type pH meter was used to measure pH of the test solution to 9.20 ± 0.10 , adjusted with dilute solution of NaOH and HCl (A.R.).

The depolariser and ligands (glycine and malonic acid) were taken in the concentration ratio 1 : 50 and current-voltage curves were drawn at different pH. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ is maximum at pH 9.20 ± 0.10 and hence the same pH was chosen for the present study. Identical conditions were maintained in simple and mixed complexes for determining the values of stability constants.

A number of current-voltage curves were obtained for binary complexes prior to the study of ternary complexes.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} gives a well defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M KCl⁵. The single wave was observed in each set of test solution. All the plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ gave straight lines with slope $30 \pm \text{mV}$ (mean value) showing two-electron reversible reduction wave of Cd^{II} and its complexes.

Cd-glycinate system: Glycine behaves as an acid and a base in water⁶. Its pK values ($\text{p}K_1 = 2.40$

and $pK_a=9.30$) have been obtained by titration method⁷. The present study has been carried out at pH 9.20 ± 0.10 so as to facilitate easily the complex formation.

Current-voltage curves were obtained at pH 9.20 ± 0.10 and $\mu=1.00 M$ KCl. The concentrations of glycine were varied from 0.001 to 0.01 M. The values of half-wave potentials for metal ions and their complexes shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. The nature of all the waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled. A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{gly}]$ resulted a smooth curve indicating the formation of successive complexes. A method of Deford and Hume⁸ was applied to determine the values of stability constants of three successive complexes, viz. $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})]^{+2}$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})_3]^{-1}$. The values of stability constants are $\log \beta_{10}=4.00$, $\log \beta_{20}=6.47$ and $\log \beta_{30}=9.86$. The data have been presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{10} VALUES FOR Cd-GLYCINATE SYSTEM

[Cd^{II}]= $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$ KCl, pH= 9.20 ± 0.10 , Temp.= 42° $E_{1/2}$ OF Cd^{II}= $-0.610 V$ vs S.C.E.

[Gly] M	$E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_p/I_c$	$F_{00}[X]$	$F_{10}[X] \times 10^4$	$F_{20}[X] \times 10^6$	$F_{30}[X] \times 10^9$
0.000	—	—	1.00	—	—	—
0.001	0.035	0.021	16.04	1.50	5.00	—
0.002	0.060	0.021	112.56	5.57	22.85	9.92
0.003	0.070	0.037	254.56	8.45	24.83	7.21
0.004	0.080	0.044	563.89	14.07	32.67	7.41
0.005	0.090	0.061	1 378.20	25.54	49.08	9.21
0.006	0.095	0.069	1 922.20	32.02	51.70	8.11
0.007	0.100	0.069	2 837.91	40.52	56.45	7.63
0.008	0.105	0.069	4 189.86	52.36	64.20	7.65
0.010	0.115	0.077	5 636.37	56.35	—	—

$\log \beta_{10}=4.00$, $\log \beta_{20}=6.47$, $\log \beta_{30}=9.86$.

Cd-malonate system: Lingane⁹ method was used to determine the values of stability constants of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes of Cd^{II} with malonic acid. The values of stability constants for $[\text{Cd}(\text{mal})]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{mal})_2]^{-2}$ were $\log \beta_{01}=2.70$ and $\log \beta_{02}=3.80$, respectively.

Cd-glycinate-malonate system: The Cd-Gly-Mal system was studied keeping the concentration of malonic acid constant at 0.005 and 0.001 M while varying the concentration of glycine from 0.001 to 0.01 M at pH 9.20 ± 0.10 and $\mu=1.0 M$ KCl. The nature of each wave was reversible and diffusion-controlled.

Following the method of Schaap and McMaster¹⁰ for treatment of the data, the function F_{00} , F_{10} , F_{20} and F_{30} sets of values for A, B, C and D, were obtained for each system. Three mixed complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})(\text{mal})]^{-1}$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})(\text{mal})_2]^{-3}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})_2(\text{mal})]^{-2}$ are formed. Their stability constants values are $\log \beta_{11}=6.48$, $\log \beta_{12}=8.30$ and $\log \beta_{21}=8.54$, respectively. The results are cited in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{10} VALUES FOR Cd-GLYCINATE-MALONATE SYSTEM

[Malonate]= $0.005 M$ (fixed), $\mu=1.0 M$ KCl, Temp.= 42° pH= 9.20 ± 0.10 , $E_{1/2}$ OF Cd^{II}= $-0.60 V$ vs S.C.E.

[Gly] M	$E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_p/I_c$	$F_{00}[X,Y]$	$F_{10}[X,Y] \times 10^4$	$F_{20}[X,Y] \times 10^6$	$F_{30}[X,Y] \times 10^9$
0.000	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.001	0.030	0.022	10.89	—	—	—
0.002	0.062	0.022	130.18	6.38	16.92	—
0.003	0.073	0.022	310.60	10.27	24.28	—
0.004	0.083	0.037	700.10	17.44	36.10	7.52
0.005	0.091	0.037	1 307.49	26.09	46.18	8.03
0.006	0.097	0.037	2 080.68	34.63	52.72	7.78
0.007	0.102	0.052	3 180.92	45.40	60.58	7.79
0.008	0.106	0.061	4 446.72	55.55	65.68	7.46
0.010	0.116	0.061	9 690.26	96.87	93.87	8.78

$\log A=0.397$, $\log B=4.47$, $\log C=6.77$, $\log D=9.88$.

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{10} VALUES FOR Cd-GLYCINATE-MALONATE SYSTEM

[Malonate]= $0.01 M$ (fixed), $\mu=1.0 M$ KCl, pH= 9.20 ± 0.10 , Temp.= 42° , $E_{1/2}$ OF Cd^{II}= $-0.610 V$ vs S.C.E.

[Gly] M	$E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_p/I_c$	$F_{00}[X,Y]$	$F_{10}[X,Y] \times 10^4$	$F_{20}[X,Y] \times 10^6$	$F_{30}[X,Y] \times 10^9$
0.000	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.001	0.034	0.023	14.91	—	—	—
0.002	0.063	0.037	147.54	7.12	5.63	—
0.003	0.074	0.045	354.12	11.63	18.76	—
0.004	0.086	0.045	902.06	22.42	41.05	9.26
0.005	0.094	0.045	1 692.51	33.55	55.10	10.22
0.006	0.100	0.062	2 792.54	46.45	67.41	9.05
0.007	0.104	0.062	3 813.81	54.41	61.15	9.30
0.008	0.108	0.079	5 416.51	67.64	77.05	9.63
0.010	0.117	0.079	10 921.44	109.16	103.16	10.31

$\log A=0.61$, $\log B=4.77$, $\log C=6.60$, $\log D=9.97$.

For a comparison of the stabilities of simple and mixed complexes, it is convenient to calculate the values of mixing constants $\log K_m$ using the relation¹¹,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 (\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20})$$

Hence, $\log K_m=1.33$. The positive value of $\log K_m$ indicates that mixed complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{gly})(\text{mal})]$ is more stable than the simple binary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and malonic acid.

The results of the present study are given in Chart 1.

Chart 1

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Chemical Studies on some $\text{Ni}(\text{amine})_n^+ \text{MoO}_4^{2-}$ Complexes

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In our previous paper, we communicated some structural aspects of amine complexes of Ni^{II} having WO_4^{2-} as anion¹. In this communication, we report the preparation and characterisation of some complexes of Ni^{II} with various amines having MoO_4^{2-} as anion. The complexes have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic, infrared, electronic spectra and X-ray powder diffraction data. The aim of investigation is to study the coordination behaviour of Ni^{II} in presence of a different anion.

Experimental

The starting material nickel molybdate was prepared by the reported method². The complexes were isolated by shaking nickel molybdate (0.01 mol) with the required amine (0.03 mol) in ethanol (~100 ml). The contents were shaken for ~12 h. The complexation was marked by change in colour from light yellow to violet/purple/pink. The products were filtered washed 3-4 times with ethanol. The complexes were dissolved in distilled water and recrystallised, and washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} before analysis.

Nickel and molybdenum in the complexes were determined gravimetrically as bis-glyoximate nickel(II) and lead molybdate, respectively³. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were analysed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes were determined by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as standard. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The X-ray powder pattern was recorded on a diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ ($\lambda=1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at I.I.T., Bombay. The diffractogram was obtained at scanning speed of $1^\circ (2\theta) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and chart speed 2 cm min^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reports the analytical, magnetic and conductance data. From elemental analyses the molecular formulae of complexes work out to be $\text{NiL}_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{L}=\text{en}$, $\text{NiL}_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{L}=\text{Pn}$, and $\text{NiL}_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ for $\text{L}=\text{dien}$. The magnetic moment values of the complexes lie in the range 2.99-3.18 B.M., which are in good agreement with the reported values of Ni^{II} complexes in octahedral field (2.92-3.41 B.M.) corresponding to two unpaired electrons^{4,5}. The molar conductance values ($227-247 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate the ionic nature of the complexes⁶.

The electronic spectra of the complexes show three prominent bands at 13 106-13 172 (ν_1), 18 488-18 867 (ν_2) and 30 556-29 872 (ν_3) which correspond to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$, respectively. The band positions suggest the octahedral geometry of the six-coordinate complexes^{7,8}. The B values vary from 637 to 668 cm^{-1} . The Racah parameter have been found to be 60% for $\text{Ni}(\text{dien})_3\text{MoO}_4$, 63% for $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3\text{MoO}_4$ and 68% for $\text{Ni}(\text{Pn})_3\text{MoO}_4$ of the free ion value (1 080 cm^{-1})⁹. This could be due to distortion of the O_h symmetry in aqueous solution of the complexes.

The comparison of the ir spectra of pure ligands and those of complexes has been made. The assignments of ir spectra have been given on the basis of reported ir data of the amine complexes^{10,11}. A negative shift in N-H stretching have been noted in all the complexes. The N-H vibrations in various complexes appear as follows: $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 3 260m, 3 220m and 3 110m (in free ligand 3 305, 3 290); $\text{Ni}(\text{Pn})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 3 250m and 3 120s on the lower energy side than the free ligands (3 260s and 3 320s); diethylenetriamine 3 340s, 3 250s and 3 160m but in the complex these bands appears at 3 320s, 3 179s, 3 119s. All complexes show a broad band around 3 500 cm^{-1} and weak band around 1 600 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of water of crystallisation^{12,13}. The ir band due to oxo anion MoO_4^{2-} in these complexes were identified as follows. In the complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{Pn})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{dien})_3\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 appear at